

FACTORS FOR IMPROVING THE ADMINISTRATIVE SYSTEM IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Abstract: This is it article "Education quality in lifting management It was prepared on the topic of "Factors of improving the system", to get acquainted with the fundamentally reformed education system in our society and to determine their place in our life today, to ensure the high quality of training of mature personnel. is directed.

Key words: National personnel training program, century of intellectual development, information-analytical function, goal-motivational function, organizational-executive function

Introduction: In our country education to the system the country stable progressive attention as an important factor of development began to show its effect in a short period of time. This is also recognized by the international community. Of course, in the years of independence, large-scale reforms were implemented on the basis of the National Personnel Training Program. Modern achievements of science and technology based on education programs by improving is going naturally under such conditions education manage in the system pedagogical the process scientific basically There are urgent tasks such as organizing, conducting research on positive solutions to the problems arising in the activity will come.

At the recent special session of the Tashkent City Council of People's Deputies, our President focused on a number of tasks that are extremely important and relevant for today, and the rapidly developing in time to the body coming brand new requirements they emphasized the need for every person to deeply understand, change his attitude to work and life, no matter where and in what position he works. In particular, the following comments made by the President encouraged every countryman, especially the responsible leaders working in the management system, to be more responsible and vigilant: We often say that the 21st century is the century of intellectual development since today's in the day leader not only sure one of the profession the owner, first of all, to the people's trust with his activity and humanity to be worthy, possessing high intellectual thinking, far-seeing, always new aspire to time with step by step being living persistent In fact, it is necessary for the director of the school to organize the management of the educational institution in modern ways. If the head of a general secondary educational institution does not have the necessary knowledge, experience, pedagogical skills, skills and qualifications in the areas of management, various problems that arise in the management of the educational process its inability to find a reasonable solution in time becomes noticeable. One of the most basic conditions for preventing them and improving the activities of pedagogical staff and, as a result, the development of the educational process is the organization of management activities on a scientific basis. Our nation has a rich historical and cultural history of the oriental approach to

leading personnel and their characteristics. There are traditions, as evidenced by Abu Prose Pharaoh by reported of the leader virtue about bring up ideas possible

- a) In that case, the leader is sensitive and insightful by nature, and clearly imagines the general situation take;
- b) who keeps events in his memory completely; sharp mind and smart, own his opinion beautiful words with representing obvious able to explain;
- c) He is eager for education, knowledge and enlightenment, and from his hardships not fleeing;
- d) who loves truth and truth, righteous and true people, hates lies and liars;
- e) self-respecting, self-respecting; emphasizing his human qualities such as being fair by nature and being determined, steadfast, courageous, and brave in implementing the measures he considers necessary passed.

Based on this, it can be said that even today school management works in efficiency of the leader personal qualities important has a place. In fact, we have witnessed many times in the experience that the personality of the director and his moral qualities have a direct impact on the collaborative innovative activities of team members and a healthy creative environment. Here is an interesting fact that takes into account the general aspects listed above without education institution leaders field from the essence It is observed that there are also unique personal characteristics that arise. In particular, their easy access to communication, openness, activeness in establishing mutual relations, intellectual development, sensitivity to emotions one can cite his indulgence, dislike of rudeness, cheerfulness as an example. In the organization and management of modern school activities, all employees of the educational institution should be equally satisfied with the results of their work activities, the correct division of labor in the team, the formation of a sense of responsibility in employees for their tasks, the current educational process The efficiency of organization on a scientific basis at the level of modern requirements depends to a large extent on the extent to which the leaders of the educational institution understand and implement their functional tasks. In the management of the educational institution, it is important to monitor the process of interaction between pedagogic staff, parents and students, and to create a necessary and comfortable mental environment for everyone. For this, the existing relations in the educational institution, the factors influencing the physical, mental and intellectual development of students, i.e. teachers and students, parents with education institution and students should be well aware of the relationship between them. Timely identification of negative situations that may occur in the process and determination of the most optimal ways of influencing it, collecting reliable information about the state of the educational process, processing and In the objective assessment, the aforementioned information is very important.

It should be noted here that the principal of the school is the main goal of the educational institution, which is of special importance in the organization and development of the educational work, information-analysis, purposeful-motivation. , it is necessary to systematically and correctly implement the functions of foresight-planning, organization-execution, control-diagnosis and regulation-coordination. So, what is their essence?

The information-analysis function is of particular importance in management, and the acquisition and analysis of information is the foundation of the management system. The

first goal is to regularly collect information about pedagogical systems (pedagogical process), study them in depth and objectively evaluate them. On the basis of the obtained conclusions, it is necessary to establish the management strategy, development factors, specific measures, organize and monitor their implementation. Therefore, information should be reliable, new and useful.

In the implementation of **the purpose-motivational function**, first of all, the **educational institution** forward placed the goal common that and there is it is necessary to take into account conditions and situations. Also in the distribution of tasks of goals unity storage, of assignments To involve the executors in the process of setting the goal for timely and effective implementation, to understand in advance about the expected results have to be assignments analysis done their fulfillment it is necessary to clearly define the term. Taking into account the characteristics of motives, that is, their which one management activities right to direct which ones It is important to know that it creates an opportunity to create an effective action plan.

The precognition-planning function determines the organizational forms, methods, and influencing tools, evaluates the norms and results of control. service does. also pedagogical system and his provides an opportunity to coordinate and regulate the activities of the participants. Therefore, the leader should determine the state of the educational institution, the achieved results, development opportunities and dynamics, study the mental environment, mutual relations and needs in the team, and determine the strategy to create a process of interaction that is convenient for everyone. forms the basis of the prevision-planning function is enough.

The organizational-executive function is expressed in all directions of management activity. That is, it is related to the selection and placement of personnel, the formation of the interaction system of the performers, the collection and processing of information. As a result, a structural system specific to a certain pedagogical management is created. Its effective implementation is mutual trust and support, everyone's choice the right to give only the goal it's not, perhaps to him reach It is related to defining the criteria, creating conditions for employees to fully demonstrate their personal capabilities and abilities, encouraging initiative and objectively evaluating the work of each employee, creating a healthy social and psychological environment in the team. ``special importance profession is enough.

Control-diagnostic function. Control is related to all functions performed in the management process. Pedagogical system management in the process intended from the direction known one in a sense deviations too to the body coming possible Exactly so situations road Control has a very important role in determining the cause of the errors and determining the methods of their correction important.

The regulation-coordinating function is necessary for the state of the pedagogical system, defined level holding to stand him new quality level serves to raise and correct mistakes made in the pedagogical process and to regulate the behavior of participants. Activity of subjects of the pedagogical system using this function mutually coordinated. In turn, coordination requires a high level of speed in the coordination of all links with the direction of movement of the pedagogical system.

CONCLUSION.

To sum up, modern school management is a complex, multi-component organizational structure, where the main goal is to prepare students for life, their independent work and complex socio-economic conditions. It is important to unite the efforts of all subjects in the educational institution towards this goal, to create an environment of mutual cooperation in order to ensure their adaptation

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